

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic Interactions and Taxon Names Found within millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens
hash://md5/74ce739250fb9072420a1fc65440f527

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens, has fingerprint hash://md5/74ce739250fb9072420a1fc65440f527, is 15.6MiB in size and contains 34,180 interactions with 2 unique types of associations (e.g., eats) between 4,127 primary taxa (e.g., *Lymantria dispar*) and 3,374 associated taxa (e.g., *Homo sapiens*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Sarah E Miller. 12/13/2016. Species associations manually extracted from Onstad, D.W. EDWIP: Ecological Database of the World’s Insect Pathogens. Champaign, Illinois: Illinois Natural History Survey, [23/11/2016]. <http://insectweb.inhs.uiuc.edu/Pathogens/EDWIP>.
<https://zenodo.org/records/258220/files/millirse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens-v1.0.zip> 2026-06-06T15:06:10.277Z hash://md5/74ce739250fb9072420a1fc65440f527

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 15.6MiB) under review
elton pull millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens

# generate review notes
elton review millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](https://github.com/millerse/check-data.sh). See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named millerse/Ecological-Database-of-the-World-s-Insect-Pathogens, has fingerprint hash://md5/74ce739250fb9072420a1fc65440f527,

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

is 15.6MiB in size and contains 34,180 interactions with 2 unique types of associations (e.g., eats) between 4,127 primary taxa (e.g., *Lymantria dispar*) and 3,374 associated taxa (e.g., *Homo sapiens*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Cydia pomonella	hasPathogen	Steinernema carpocapsae	Peters, A., 1996. The natural host range of <i>Steinernema</i> and <i>Heterorhabditis</i> spp. and their impact on insect populations. <i>Biocontrol Science and Technology</i> 6: 389-402.; Sandner, H. and Seryczynska, H., 1971. Changes in the ultrastructure of the fat-body of <i>Galleria mellonella</i> L. under the influence of invasion by <i>Neoplectana carpocapsae</i> Weiser (Nematoda, Steinernemati- dae). <i>Bull. l'Acad. Pol. Sci.</i> 19: 67-69.

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Cydia pomonella	hasPathogen	Steinernema carpocapsae	Vinciguerra, M. T. and Tacconi, R., 1983. Variabilita morfologica di Neoaplectana carpocapsae Weiser, 1955 (Rhabditida, Nematoda) rinvenuta in larve di Laspeyresia pomonella (L.). Bolletino del Istituto di Entomologia "Guido Grandi", Universita di Bologna (Italy) 38:89-94.; Peters, A., 1996. The natural host range of Steinernema and Heterorhabditis spp. and their impact on insect populations. Biocontrol Science and Technology 6: 389-402.
Cydia pomonella	hasPathogen	Steinernema carpocapsae	Jackson, G. J., 1965. Differentiation of three species of Neoaplectana (Nematoda: Rhabditida), grown axenically. Parasitol. 55: 571-578.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Agrotis segetum	hasPathogen	Steinernema carpocapsae	Peters, A., 1996. The natural host range of Steinernema and Heterorhabditis spp. and their impact on insect populations. Biocontrol Science and Technology 6: 389-402.; Stanuszek, S. 1970. Neoaplectana feltiae (Filipjev, 1934) –a facultative parasite of the caterpillars of Agrotinae in Poland. Zesz. Probl. Postępów Nauk Roln. 154: 331-360.

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	23541
hasPathogen	10639

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Lymantria dispar	2149
Trichoplusia ni	815
Cydia pomonella	610

sourceTaxonName	count
Ostrinia nubilalis	490
Spodoptera frugiperda	415
Otiorhynchus sulcatus	382
Choristoneura fumiferana	345
Lepidosaphes beckii	323
Leptinotarsa decemlineata	317
Helicoverpa zea	294
Pieris rapae	279
Melolontha melolontha	272
Bemisia tabaci	270
Spodoptera exigua	267
Quadraspidiotus perniciosus	265
Acyrtosiphon pisum	255
Anopheles gambiae	249
Helicoverpa armigera	246
Tetranychus urticae	239

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Homo sapiens	755
Prunus	693
Zea mays	601
NPV	542
Beauveria bassiana	537
Malus	531
Solanum tuberosum	413
Quercus	391
Metarhizium anisopliae	357
Pinus	335
Glycine max	320
Phaseolus	317
Salix	317
Acer	311
Populus	303
Medicago sativa	301
Citrus	299
Cypovirus	284
Gossypium hirsutum	276

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Lymantria dispar	eats	Populus	127
Lymantria dispar	eats	Alnus	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Quercus	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Acer	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Thuja occidentalis	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Salix	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Malus	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Pinus	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Crataegus	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Fagus	126
Lymantria dispar	eats	Carya	125
Cydia pomonella	eats	Prunus	122
Aedes aegypti	eats	fungi	110
Lymantria dispar	eats	Tsuga	102
Lymantria dispar	eats	Picea	102
Lymantria dispar	eats	Nyssa sylvatica	102
Lymantria dispar	eats	Pseudotsuga menziesii	102
Lymantria dispar	eats	Tilia americana	102
Lymantria dispar	eats	Sassafras albidum	102

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
```


Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

PROJECTION
  "init=epsg:4326"
END
LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
  NAME      "modis_nasa"
  TYPE      RASTER
  OFFSITE   0 0 0
  STATUS    ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
  CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR      232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE NULL NULL
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abisares gerstaeckeri	NONE	col	Abisares gerstaeckeri
Ablabechnia lentiginosa	NONE	col	Ablabechnia lentiginosa
Acanthopplusia agnata	NONE	col	Acanthopplusia agnata
Acanthospora crypturgi	NONE	col	Acanthospora crypturgi

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	1970
col	family	3
col	genus	682
col	kingdom	1
col	order	1
col	species	4664
col	subgenus	16
col	subspecies	205
col	subtribe	1
col	variety	16

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
discoverlife	NA	7408
discoverlife	species	25
gbif	NA	1877
gbif	family	2
gbif	form	2
gbif	genus	682
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	1
gbif	species	4761
gbif	subspecies	194
gbif	variety	31
itis	NA	4918
itis	family	2
itis	genus	524
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	1
itis	phylum	1
itis	species	1929
itis	subgenus	1
itis	subspecies	51
itis	variety	9
mdd	NA	7433
ncbi	NA	3321
ncbi	family	3
ncbi	genus	634
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	1
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	3410
ncbi	subfamily	1
ncbi	subgenus	20
ncbi	subspecies	55
ncbi	varietas	2
pbdb	NA	6949
pbdb	class	1
pbdb	family	2
pbdb	genus	325
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	1
pbdb	species	153
pbdb	suborder	1
pbdb	subtribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
tpt	NA	7348
tpt	genus	5
tpt	order	1
tpt	species	79
wfo	NA	6546
wfo	family	1
wfo	genus	349
wfo	species	529
wfo	subspecies	17
wfo	variety	11
worms	NA	6572
worms	family	2
worms	genus	368
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	1
worms	species	486
worms	subspecies	5

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	1982
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4759
col	SYNONYM_OF	2453
discoverlife	NONE	7445
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	7
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	22
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	2
gbif	NONE	1888
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5282
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	2335
itis	NONE	4933
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2372
itis	SYNONYM_OF	247
mdd	NONE	7464
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
ncbi	NONE	3332
ncbi	SAME_AS	3729
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	459
pdb	NONE	6974
pdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	489
pdb	SYNONYM_OF	32
tpt	NONE	7385
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	67
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	146
wfo	NONE	6565
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	813
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	195
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	80
worms	NONE	6596
worms	SYNONYM_OF	85
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	869

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-08T01:09:16Z	note	failed to lookup [GEONAMES:798544] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/get.JSON?formatted=true&geonameId=798544&username=globi&style=full] not found]
2026-06-08T01:09:16Z	note	failed to lookup [GEONAMES:3175395] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/get.JSON?formatted=true&geonameId=3175395&username=globi&style=full] not found]
2026-06-08T01:09:16Z	note	failed to lookup [GEONAMES:798544] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/get.JSON?formatted=true&geonameId=798544&username=globi&style=full] not found]
2026-06-08T01:09:16Z	note	failed to lookup [GEONAMES:6252001] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/get.JSON?formatted=true&geonameId=6252001&username=globi&style=full] not found]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
failed to lookup [GEONAMES:6252001] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/get.JSON?formatted=true&geonameId=6252001&username=globi&style=full] not found]	7221

reviewComment	count
failed to lookup [GEONAMES:1861060] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/getJSON?formatted=true&geonameId=1861060&username=globi&style=full] not found]	2842
failed to lookup [GEONAMES:3017382] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/getJSON?formatted=true&geonameId=3017382&username=globi&style=full] not found]	1225
failed to lookup [GEONAMES:6251999] because of: [resource [http://api.geonames.org/getJSON?formatted=true&geonameId=6251999&username=globi&style=full] not found]	1209

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-08) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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